

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online at :

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2issue-6-july-2014>

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Instructions for authors and subscription information:

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MULTIVARIATE GARCH MODEL OF TRANSMISSION OF VOLATILITY: A STUDY OF BRIC STOCK MARKETS

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Abstract

The study examines the volatility spillover among BRIC markets using a four-variable symmetric GARCH-BEKK model during January 2009 to June 2014. We find evidence of bi-directional shock spill over among Brazil and Russia, Brazil and China, Russia and India and bidirectional volatility spill over among stock markets of Brazil and Russia, between Brazil and India and among Brazil and China. The magnitude of volatility linkages is low indicating weak integration of BRIC stock markets. The study finds that own volatility spillover is higher than cross market spillover. The overall persistence of stock market volatility is highest for China (0.987) and lowest for Russia (0.889). The implication of weak integration is that investors will benefit from reduction of diversifiable risk.

Keywords: Return and Volatility spillovers, Unit Root Test, Multivariate GARCH model, **JEL Classification:** C32, G15

1. Introduction

The extent of the global linkage of emerging markets improves access to the international capital markets. Strong global linkage reduces the insulation of the emerging stock markets from external shocks, hence limiting the scope for independent monetary policy (Li and Majerowska, 2007). From the perspective of the global investors, weak stock market linkage in the form of less than perfect correlation between their returns offers potential gains from international portfolio diversification, while strong market linkage or co-movement in returns eliminates the potential benefits of diversification.

Although there is no dearth of literature on financial integration, there are only a few studies related to emerging stock markets of Asia. Moreover, the limited literature on the emerging stock markets in Asia has studied the co-movements between the stock markets using cointegration and Vector Autoregression framework (Eun and Shin, 1989, Chung and Ng, 1992, Bhattacharya and Samantha, 2001, Wong, Agrawal and Du, 2005, Voronkova, 2004, Ahmad, Ashraf and Ahmed, 2005, Cheeley and Steeley, 2005, Yang, Hsiao, Li and Wang, 2006, Hoque, 2007). The studies do not take into account the interactions in terms of volatility among the markets.

It is believed that if markets are integrated, an unanticipated event in one market will influence not only returns but also variance in the other markets. The analysis of volatility is particularly important because it can proxy for the risk of assets.

Joshi(2011) examined the return and volatility spillover among Asian stock markets in India, Hong Kong, Japan, China, Jakarta and Korea using a six-variable asymmetric GARCH-BEKK model during 2nd February 2007 to 20th February, 2010. The study found the evidence of bi-directional return; shock and volatility spill over among most of the stock markets. The magnitude of volatility linkages was low indicating weak integration of Asian stock markets. It found that own market volatility spillover was higher than cross market spillover.

Li (2007) examined the linkages between the two emerging stock exchanges namely Shanghai and Shenzhen of China and the established stock markets Heng Seng of Hong Kong and S & P of the US by a multivariate GARCH-BEKK framework using the daily share price indices of the stock markets, January 4, 2000 to August 17, 2005. The results indicated that there was no evidence of spillover effect in terms of return and volatility between the stock exchanges in China and US market. There was an evidence of unidirectional volatility spillover from stock exchange in Hong Kong to those in Shanghai and Shenzhen. The study found that Chinese stock exchanges were integrated with the regional developed stock exchange in Hong Kong but the extent of the linkages between the stock exchange in Hong Kong and China was weak. The results further showed that there was a bidirectional shock spillover between the two Chinese stock exchanges. The study also found that there was an asymmetric response of volatility in all four stock exchanges under study.

Harris and Pisedtasalasai (2006) applied constant conditional correlation MGARCH framework to investigate return and volatility spillover effects between the Financial Times Stock Exchange (FTSE)100, FTSE 200 and FTSE small cap equity indices of UK stock market using daily return during January 1, 1986 to December 2002 using GJR specifications of MGARCH model to capture asymmetric effect. The study found that return and volatility transmission mechanism between large and small stocks in the UK were asymmetric. There were significant positive spillover effects from portfolio of larger stocks to the portfolio of smaller stocks.

Worthington and Higgs (2004) examined the transmission of equity returns and volatility among three developed Asian markets (Hong Kong, Japan and Singapore) and six emerging markets of Asia (Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, the Philippines, Taiwan and Thailand) using weekly returns from January 15, 1988 to October 6, 2000. They employed BEKK (Baba, Engle, Kraft and Kroner) parameterization of multivariate GARCH model to identify the source and magnitude of volatility spillover. The study found the presence of positive mean and volatility spillovers. The mean return spillovers from the developed markets to the emerging markets were not homogenous across the emerging markets. Application of MGARCH suggested that own stock market volatility spillovers were generally higher than cross-volatility spillovers for all markets, especially for emerging stock markets.

Scheicher(2001) studied the regional and global integration of stock markets in terms of return and volatility shocks in Hungary, Poland and Czech Republic and Financial Times/S&P's world actuaries index by using MGARCH(Multivariate Generalized Auto regressive conditional heteroscedasticity) with a constant conditional correlation. Using daily closing price values of the stock markets from January 1, 1995 to October 7, 1997, results revealed that the emerging stock exchanges were integrated with the

global market, proxied by Financial Times/S&P's actuaries' world index only in terms of return. MGARCH results showed that the regional influences were the major cause of volatility of the markets. International volatility had no impact on the markets.

Chou, Lin and Wu (1999) examined the price and volatility linkages of Taiwan stock market with United States using close-to-open, open-to-close and close-to-close returns of indices of Taiwan known as Taikex and United states' Standard and Poor's 500 (S&P 500) composite index during January 1, 1991 to December 31, 1994. The results found that the volatility and return spilt over from US to Taiwan. The results of MGARCH indicated some important linkage from the US stock market to the Taiwan stock market. The spillover effects occurred for both the mean and the variance of Taiwan Stock returns. It further pointed out that the volatility in US stock markets affected total daily volatilities of the Taiwan stock market.

Although there is a voluminous literature on equity market integration internationally, little research has been undertaken to study the interdependence structure of the BRIC stock markets. BRIC stands for Brazil, Russia, India and China. These countries were originally grouped in to BRICs by Goldman Sachs's James O'Neal. BRIC countries are formed because of their crucial role in the today's world economy. The Figure 1 highlights the importance of the BRICs in the world's future economy as they may become the largest economies in the world by 2050 (Glodman Sachs¹). The economic growth rates for these countries are well above the most of the industrialized countries like USA, Japan,

Figure 1: Ten Largest Economy of the World in 2050, measuerd in GDP(billions of 2006 USD)

Source: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Top_five_largest_economies_in_2050.jpg

United Kingdom and Canada. During 2002 – 2008, the Chinese economy grew at an average of 10 percent per year while India grew at an average of 8 percent per year (Balakrishnan et el 2009). China also gradually became the world's largest exporter with \$1,897 trillion worth of exports (CIA's The Worlds Fact book 2011). Meanwhile, the BRICs are also increasing their trade with one another: especially the Chinese and Indian trade has increased by \$60 billion in 2010 while setting a \$100 billion bilateral trade target by 2015. The BRICs' large share of foreign exchange reserves in the world economy provides them a strong competitive advantage. All four countries are among the ten largest accumulators of foreign exchange reserves in dollars, accounting for over 40 percent of the world's total ("The trillion Dollar Baby", The Economist Magazine February 2012).

¹ Goldman Sachs : <http://www.goldmansachs.com/>

Moreover, the monetary policy actions of BRICs can influence the rest of the world as they hold a large portion of treasury bonds of many of the foreign countries including the US, UK and Canada. All these above factors make the BRICs highly important in the world economy. So having a better idea about the monetary policy behavior of the BRICs would help other economies to be efficient in their participation in the world economic activities (Tamazian & Chousa, 2009). With the growing importance of BRIC countries in the world economy, it will be interesting to examine how those market interact with each other especially in terms of volatility. The knowledge about volatility interactions will help investors to take investment and portfolio diversification decision. Weak stock market linkages benefits investors from international portfolio diversification, while strong market linkage in returns and volatility eliminates the potential benefits of diversification.

In the light of the review of the existing literature on the linkages between the various stock markets, the present study tries to analyze volatility spill over among BRIC stock markets using MGARCH-BEKK framework. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Data and Preliminary Analysis are presented in Section 2. Section 3 provides research design used in the study. Empirical results are discussed in Section 4. Section 5 summarizes.

2. Data and Preliminary Analysis

We collected data on BOVASPA, RTSI, Sensex and SSE of Brazil, Russia, India and China's closing price indices respectively from January 1, 2009 to June, 2014. It consists of 1359 observations. The period is the most recent one. These stock markets have become increasingly integrated. The trades between countries have increased. They are playing an important role in the world economy. These might have influenced the behavior and the pattern of volatility and therefore it will be instructive to study volatility in this period.

Figure 1 presents time plot of the price series of BRIC stock markets. The first impression is that all the indices have somewhat a similar movement. It can be noticed that all the indices declined after mid 2007. Overall, all the stock price indices are trending upwards during the recent time.

Figure 2 represents the returns of the share price indices, the first difference of the natural logarithm of the share price indices, during the period under study. All four indices are characterized by volatility clustering where large (small) volatility followed by large (small) volatility. As the cluster tends to occur simultaneously, between the indices, volatility must be modeled systematically.

Figure 2: Stock indices during year 2001 to year 2010.

Figure 3: Returns of the share price indices

Table 1 reports the summary statistics for the return series.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Daily Returns

Statistic	Bovaspa	RTSI	Sensex	SSE
Mean	0.00021	0.00055	0.00071	0.00006
Standard deviation	0.01483	0.01985	0.01342	0.01333
Skewness	-0.05348	-0.20030	1.14196	-0.37298
Kurtosis	4.94187	6.63919	18.95906	5.46130
Jarque-Bera Statistics	241.01(0.000)	758.45(0.000)	14706.5(0.000)	374.27(0.000)
Q ² (12)	167.73(0.000)	207.46(0.000)	62.96(0.000)	201.78(0.000)
ARCH LM statistics (at Lag =1)	12.43(0.000)	28.58(0.000)	1.09(0.29)	3.15(0.076)
ARCH LM statistics (at Lag =5)	75.41(0.000)	67.82(0.000)	11.59(0.041)	55.35(0.000)

Bovaspa, RTSI, Sensex and SSE represent daily returns of Brazil, Russia, India and Chinese stock indices.

The performance of the indices as measured by the average return is better in Sensex stock market followed by Russia, Brazil and China stock markets. The average return of stock markets of China and Japan are negative. The Russian stock market exhibits higher volatility than other stock markets under study. The Jarque-Bera statistics reject the null hypothesis that the returns are normally distributed for all cases. All Stock indices except India have negative skewness, indicating that large negative stock returns are more common than large positive returns. In contrast, Furthermore all the returns series are leptokurtic, having significantly fatter tails and higher peaks which can be seen from the kurtosis statistics that are greater than 3. Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) models are capable of dealing with data displaying the above features. When modelling with GARCH, the nonzero skewness statistics indicate an ARCH order higher than one in the conditional variance equation. Subsequently, a Multivariate GARCH (1, 1) model should be preferred to an ARCH (*p*) model to examine volatility spillover effects for the sake of parsimony (Li, 2007).

3. Methodology

On the basis of the features discussed in the previous section, GARCH model is appropriate for the study. The aim of the paper is to examine the interdependence across the four stock markets. The following model is used to examine the joint process relating to the share price indices under study.

$$Y_t = \alpha + \Gamma Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t,$$

$$\varepsilon_t / I_{t-1} \approx N(0, H_t)$$

Equation 1

Where Y_t is a 4×1 vector of daily returns at time t and Γ is a 4×4 matrix for parameters associated with the lagged returns. The diagonal elements in matrix Γ , γ_{ii} , measure the effect of own past returns while the off-diagonal elements, γ_{ij} , captures the relation in terms of returns across the markets, also known as return spillover. The 4×1 vector of random error, ε_t , is the innovation for each market at time t and has a 4×4 conditional variance-covariance matrix, H_t . The market information available at time $t-1$ is represented by the information set I_{t-1} . The 4×1 vector of α represents constants. Bollerslev et al. (1988) propose that H_t is a linear function of the lagged squared errors and cross products of errors and lagged values of the elements of H_t as follows: The variance-covariance matrix H_t is presented below:

$$vech(H_t) = vech(C) + \sum_{i=1}^q A_i vech(\varepsilon_{t-1} \varepsilon_{t-1}') + \sum_{i=1}^p G_i vech(H_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=1}^p D_i vech(H_{t-i})$$

Equation 2

Where $vech$ is the operator that stacks the lower triangular portion of a symmetric matrix into a vector. The problems with this formulation are that the number of parameters to be estimated is large and restrictions on the parameters are needed to ensure that the conditional variance matrix is positive definite. Engle and Kroner (1995) propose the following new parameterization for H_t , i.e. the BEKK model, to overcome the above two problems.

$$H_t = C'C + A' \varepsilon_{t-1} \varepsilon_{t-1}' A + G'H_{t-1}G$$

Equation 3

The BEKK model provides cross-market effects in the variance equation parsimoniously and also guarantees positive semi-definiteness by working with quadratic forms.

C is 4×4 lower triangular matrix of constants while A and G are 4×4 matrices. The diagonal parameters of matrices A and G measures the effects of own past shocks and past volatility of market i on its conditional variance. The off-diagonal parameters in matrices A and G , a_{ij} and g_{ij} , measure the cross-market effects of shock and volatility, also known as volatility spillover. H_t is a variance-covariance matrix. We will use Multivariate GARCH in the style of BEKK proposed by Engle and Kroner (1995) to analyze volatility spill over among the stock markets.

The BEKK systems can be estimated using maximum likelihood method. The log likelihood function of the joint distribution is the sum of all the log likelihood functions of the conditional distributions, i.e. the sum of the logs of multivariate-normal distribution. Letting L_t be the log likelihood of observation t , n be the number of stock exchanges and L be the joint log likelihood which gives,

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^T L_t \quad L_t = n/2 \ln(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \ln |H_t| - \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_t' H_t^{-1} \varepsilon_t$$

Equation 4

4. Empirical Results

In this section, we perform unit root test to check for nonstationarity of the stock markets series. We report the estimated results about market linkages. We will look for any statistically significant cross-market effects as evidence of linkages and measures the extent of the linkages by the estimated time-varying covariances using MGARCH asymmetric model. We organize the section as follows. In section 4.1, we discuss Augmented Dickey Fuller Test (ADF) results. In section 4.2, we report the evidence of market linkages in the estimated six-variable asymmetric GARCH-BEKK model.

4.1 Unit root test results

Stationarity conditions of the stock market indices are tested by Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test (ADF). A unit root test is a statistical test for the proposition that in an autoregressive statistical model of a time series, the autoregressive parameter is one. It is a test for detecting the presence of stationarity in the series. The early and pioneering work on testing for a unit root in time series was done by Dickey and Fuller (Dickey and Fuller 1979, Fuller 1976). If the variables in the regression model are not stationary, then it can be shown that the standard assumptions for asymptotic analysis will not be valid. In other words, the usual “t-ratios” will not follow a t-distribution; hence they are inappropriate to undertake hypothesis tests about the regression parameters.

Stationarity time series is one whose mean, variance and covariance are unchanged by time shift. Nonstationary time series have time varying mean or variance or both. If a time series is nonstationary, we can study its behaviour only for a time period under consideration. It is not possible to generalize it to other time periods. It is, therefore, not useful for forecasting purpose.

The presence of unit root in a time series is tested with the help of Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test. It tests for a unit root in the univariate representation of time series. For a return series R_t , the ADF test consists of a regression of the first difference of the series against the series lagged k times as follows:

Equation 5

$$\Delta r_t = r_t - r_{t-1}; r_t = \ln(R_t)$$

$$\Delta r_t = \alpha + \delta r_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \Delta r_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

The null hypothesis is $H_0: \delta = 0$ and $H_1: \delta < 1$. The acceptance of null hypothesis implies nonstationarity.

We can transform the non stationary time series to stationary time series either by differencing or by detrending. The transformation depends upon whether the series are difference stationary or trend stationary. We report the results of unit root test in Table 2.

Table 2: Unit Root Testing of Daily Returns

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

Null Hypothesis	Test statistics								Mackinnon
	Level				First Difference				Asymptotic
Presence of Unit root									Critical value @ 1% level
	Bovasp	RTS	Sensex	SSE	Bovasp	RTS	Sensex	SSE	
Intercept	-2.97(0.08)	-2.73(0.08)	-2.25(0.18)	-1.89(0.34)	-38.21(0.00)	-33.38(0.00)	-34.60(0.00)	-36.53(0.00)	-3.44
Trend & Intercept	-3.00(0.13)	-2.67(0.25)	-2.25(0.30)	-4.25*(0.064)	-38.25(0.00)	-33.45(0.00)	-34.59(0.00)	36.59(0.00)	-3.97
Trend coefficient	-0.00 (0.06)	-0.00(0.43)	0.00(0.17)	-0.00(0.00)	-0.00(0.18)	-0.00(0.08)	-0.00(0.62)	-0.00(0.12)	
None	0.47(0.81)	0.82(0.89)	1.89(0.99)	0.12(0.72)	-38.22(0.00)	-33.36(0.00)	-34.53(0.00)	-36.55(0.00)	-2.57

.ADF statistics reported in the Table 2 show that the null hypothesis of a unit root in case of all four indices is rejected. The absolute computed values for all the indices are higher than the MacKinnon critical value at 1% level. Thus, the results show that the return series are stationary. As the results suggest that the underlying return series are stationary, our next step is to examine the stock markets' linkages.

4.2 The Evidence of stock market linkages

The time-varying variance-covariance Equation 3 are estimated simultaneously by the maximum likelihood method. Note that the stock exchanges Brazil, Russia, India and China are indexed 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. We examine the estimated results of the time varying variance-covariance Equation 3 in the system. The results of four-variable GARCH model are reported in Table 3.

Table 3 : Estimated coefficients for four variable symmetric MGARCH

	Bovaspa(i=1)	rtsi(i=2)	Sensex(i=3)	SSE(i=4)
a_{i1}	0.158 (0.00)	0.055(0.02)	0.253(0.00)	-0.062(0.02)
a_{i2}	0.124 (0.00)	-0.172(0.00)	-0.172(0.00)	-0.113(0.00)
a_{i3}	0.314 (0.22)	-0.066(0.00)	0.049(0.05)	0.047(0.04)
a_{i4}	0.107(0.00)	-0.006(0.69)	-0.059(0.01)	0.059(0.00)
g_{i1}	0.911(0.00)	-0.176(0.00)	-0.105(0.00)	-0.057(0.01)
g_{i2}	0.379(0.00)	0.889(0.00)	-0.154(0.00)	-0.026 (0.41)
g_{i3}	0.095(0.00)	0.029(0.11)	0.974(0.00)	0.022 (0.02)
g_{i4}	0.0544(0.00)	-0.009(0.50)	-0.034(0.00)	0.987(0.00)
Multivariate Q statistics(10) (standardized Residuals): 172.738(0.23)				
Multivariate ARCH : 114.93(0.15)				

Notes

- Figures in the parenthesis indicate probability values.
- Coefficients a and g captures ARCH and GARCH

Now we examine the estimated results. It can be noted that the Ljung Box Q statistics for the 10 the order and Multivariate Q statistics for 10th orders in standardized and squared standardized residuals show that there is no series dependence in the residuals indicating the appropriateness of the fitted variance-covariance equations by the six variable asymmetric BEKK model. The matrices A and G reported in Table 3 help us to examine the relationship in terms of volatility. The diagonal elements in matrix A capture the ARCH effect, while the diagonal elements in matrix G measure the GARCH effect. As shown in Table 3, the estimated diagonal parameters a_{22} through a_{44} are statistically significant implying presence of ARCH effect in the stock markets of Brazil, Russia, India and China while parameters g_{11} through g_{44} are all statistically significant, indicating a strong GARCH (1,1) process driving the conditional variances of all the indices. The magnitude of own volatility presented by GARCH parameter is highest in stock market of China followed by India, Brazil and Russia suggesting own volatility largely affect their conditional variance.

The off-diagonal elements of matrix A and G capture the cross-market effects such as shock spillover and volatility spillover among the six stock exchanges. Firstly, we find evidence of bidirectional shock transmissions between Bovaspa and RTSI, Bovaspa and SSE, between BSE and RTSI as the pairs of off-diagonal parameters a_{12} and a_{21} , a_{14} and a_{41} , a_{23} and a_{32} are statistically significant. The two way shock spillover indicates strong connection between the stock markets. The bidirectional shock spillover indicates the news about shocks in one stock exchange affect the volatility of other stock exchange and vice-versa. In terms of cross-shock spillover effects in the markets, past innovations in Brazil have the greatest effect (0.314) on future volatility in India. The significant a_{42} and a_{31} (their counter parts are insignificant) indicate unidirectional shock spillover from China to Russia, From India to Brazil.

Secondly, there are bidirectional volatility linkages between Brazil and Russia, Brazil and India, between Brazil and China as respective coefficients in g are statistically significant. It indicates that the conditional variance of one index depends on past volatility of the other index, implying strong connection between them. Own-volatility spillovers in all markets are large and significant. The overall persistence of stock market volatility is highest for China (0.987) and lowest for Russia (0.889). In terms of cross volatility persistence in the stock markets, the past volatility shocks in Brazil have effect (0.379) on the future volatility in Russia.

In the meanwhile, the statistically significant g_{32} and insignificant g_{23} indicate unidirectional volatility spillover from India to Russia. There is no bidirectional volatility linkages between Russia and China.

5. Summary

The study investigates volatility spillover effect between the stock markets in Brazil, Russia, India and China. Summary statistics of returns series of all the stock exchanges suggest that they are leptokurtic, having significantly fatter tails and higher peaks. Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) models are capable of dealing with the property of the data.

By applying a multivariate asymmetric GARCH approach to the daily stock indices, the study found evidence of linkages in terms of volatility. We find evidence of bidirectional shock transmissions between Brazil and Russia, Brazil and China and between Russia and India. In terms of cross-shock spillover effects in the markets, past innovations in Bovaspa of Brazil have the greatest effect (0.314) on future volatility in India. Our results reveal unidirectional shock spillover from China to Russia, From India to Brazil.

There are bidirectional volatility linkages between Brazil and Russia, Brazil and India, between Brazil and China. There is also unidirectional volatility spillover from India to Russia. The overall persistence of stock market volatility is highest for China (0.987) and lowest for Russia (0.889).

References:

- Ahmad, Ashraf and Ahmed (2005), "Is the Indian stock market integrated with the US and Japanese stock markets?: An empirical analysis" South Asia economic journal, 193-206.
- Bhattacharya and Samanta (2001), "A tale of two indices: the story of the NASDAQ and The Sensex", Journal of Quantitative Economics, **1(1)**, pp. 89-102.
- Bollerslev, Engle and Wooldridge (1988), "A capital asset pricing model with time-varying covariances", Journal of political economy, **96**, 116-131.
- Brooks Chris(2008), *Introductory Econometrics for Finance*, Cambridge University Press, UK.
- Chelley and Steeley (2005), "Modeling equity market integration using smooth transition analysis: a study of eastern European stock markets", Journal of International Money and Finance, **24**, 818-831.
- Chou, Lin and Wu(1999), "Modeling the Taiwan stock market and international linkages", Pacific Economic Review, **4**, 305-320.
- Chung Yin-Wong and Ng Lillian (1992), "Interactions Between the U.S. and Japan Stock Market Indices", Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money, **2(2)**, pp. 51-69.
- Dickey D. and Fuller W., (1979) 'Distribution of the estimates for Autoregressive time series with a unit root', Journal of American Statistical Association, **74**, 427-31.
- Dickey, D. & Fuller W., (1981) 'Likelihood Ratio Statistics for Autoregressive Time Series with a Unit Root', Econometrica, **49**, 1057 - 72

- Engle and Kroner(1995), “Multivariate simultaneous generalized ARCH”, *Econometric Theory*, **11**, 122-150.
- Eun C., and Shim S, (1989), “International Transmission of Stock Market Movements”, *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, **24(2)**, 241-255.
- Harris and Pisedtasalasai (2006), “Return and volatility spillovers between large and small stocks in the UK”, *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 1-16.
- Hogue (2007), “Co-movement of Bangladesh stock market with other markets: cointegration and error correction approach”, *Managerial Finance*, **33(10)**,810-820.
- Joshi (2011), “Return and Volatility Spillovers Among Asian Stock Markets”, *Sage Open*, pp.1-8. The article is available at; <http://sgo.sagepub.com/content/early/2011/06/10/2158244011413474>
- Karolyi (1995), “A Multivariate GARCH model of international transmissions of stock returns and volatility: The case of the United States and Canada”, *Journal of Business and Economic Studies*, **13(1)**, 11-24.
- Kroner, K. and Ng, V.(1998), “Modeling asymmetric comovements of asset returns”, *The review of Financial Studies*, **11**, 817-44.
- Li (2007), “International Linkages of the Chinese stock exchanges: a multivariate GARCH analysis”, *Applied Financial Economics*, **17**, 285-295.
- Ng Thiam (2002), “Stock Price Movements in South-East Asia”, *Asian Economic Journal*, **16(4)**, pp.353-77.
- Scheicher(2001), “The comovements of stock markets in Hungary, Poland and the Czech republic”, *International Journal of Finance and Economics*, **6**, 27-39.
- Voronkova (2004), “Equity market integration in Central European stock markets: A cointegration analysis with shifting regimes”, *International Review of Financial Analyst*, **13**, 633-647.
- Wing-Keung Wong & Agarwal Aman & Jun Du, (2005), "Financial Integration for India Stock Market, a Fractional Cointegration Approach," Departmental Working Papers wp501, National University of Singapore, Department of Economics.
- Worthington and Higgs (2004), “Transmission of Equity returns and volatility in Asian developed and emerging markets: A multivariate GARCH analysis”, *International Journal of Finance and Economics*, **9**, 71-80.
- Yang, Hsiao, Li and Wang (2006), “The emerging market crisis and stock market linkages: further evidence”, *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, **21**, 727-744.